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Interlinking Police Officers' Operational Stress and Level of Resiliency

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Abstract

Police officers are among the professionals known to be most exposed to critical incidents. In their quest for public safety, peace and order, they need to combat work-related stresses. This research sought to analyze the significant relationship between the operational stress and resiliency among the Regional Mobile Force Battalion (RMFB) in Region 02, Philippines, specifically to determine the levels of their operational stress and resiliency (in terms of compassion satisfaction, burnout and secondary trauma stress). A descriptive-correlation research design was used to answer the objectives of the study. The Operational Police Stress Questionnaire (McCreary & Thompson, 2006) and the Professional Quality of Life Questionnaire (Stamm, 2009) were utilized to gather the necessary data. Frequency counts, percentages, computed mean, t-test, f-test and chi-square were used to illustrate the data gathered. The RMFB have low level of operational stress, moderate level of resiliency in burnout and secondary trauma stress. A significant relationship between operational stress and resiliency was evident. It can therefore be concluded that to have the capacity to recover from operational stress, there should be high compassion satisfaction combined with moderate levels of burnout and secondary trauma stress. This embodies a more positive behavioral outcome to recuperate from a stressful situation. It is recommended to consider conducting a routine assessment of police officers' operational stress as basis for an intervention program.

Keywords: *stress, resiliency, police stress, Regional Mobile Force Battalion*

Introduction

Police stress and resiliency in the local context acknowledged the global perspective of peace, order and security as essential to the development and success of every nation is a collective obligation by many organizations both within and outside government or non-government organizations, private or public institutions. Locally, this huge task is performed by the men and women of the Philippine National Police (PNP). The PNP is a civilian police force directed by law to, among others, nurture peace and order and protect public safety. The operational measures endorsed firm observance to the Constitutional and legal pledges which every police officer's oath to protect and uphold. This is a reminder to the police officers that peace, order and security can only be achieved through lawful and ethical means. Any other means is negating to, and undermines, the ends of law enforcement.

It is common knowledge that the rigorous and regimented trainings prior entering the PNP has inculcated various stresses anent their task. However, there are intense stressful life experiences that causes a person to snap (Morris, 2007) despite trainings to be physically and mentally tough. Conway and Siegelman (1995 cited by Morris, 2007) stated that people who usually snap are the police officers, firefighters and members of the military, these jobs require them to hide their emotions due to stereotyped role depicted to be strong.

With the huge task laid on the shoulders of the police officers that has brought inevitable stresses, measuring their level of resiliency is very significant in the performance of their duty. Hence, the study at hand endeavored to look into the aforementioned constructs. It was observed that there is scarcity of research conducted around police officers' stressors and resiliency in the Filipino context, also, conducted foreign researches studied these variables separately.

Research Objectives

The general objective of the study is to investigate the operational stresses encountered by the Regional Mobile Force Battalion (RMFB) in the performance of their duties and responsibilities and how it correlates with their level of resiliency, this research sought to answer the following specific problems:

1. determine the the level of operational stress caused by the identified aspects of a police officer's work;
2. determine the police officers' level of resiliency and
3. analyze the significant relationship between the police officer's levels of operational stress and resiliency.

Literature Review

Documented literatures have recognized that stress has been an issue surrounding policing due to the nature of the work, in fact, it is among the top three most stressed professions most reported by occupational physicians and psychiatrists (Collins & Gibbs, 2003 cited by Korre, et al., 2014). The overwhelming experiences of police officers' stress include the following: death, suicide, injury, crimes, homicides and others (Webster, 2013). Other stressors can be found in the organization climate such as management stressors, everyday work-related stressors consist of attending to public concerns, dealings with the criminal justice system, and other personal struggles between the police officers' personal life and his professional life (Korre et al., 2014).

Police work results to threats to their overall functioning. In fact, the longstanding effects of stress to the policeman, to the organization,

and the general public showed continuous absenteeism, health issues, piling up of citizen complaints, exaggerated use of force and aggressiveness, excessive alcohol and drug intoxication, toxic relations with family and friends, poorer connections with the community, heightened helplessness, a tendency for depressive symptoms and suicidal thoughts, reduced contentment and satisfaction in life, and decreased quality of work performance (Schaible & Gecas, 2010; Griffin, Hogan, Lambert, Tucker-Gail, & Baker, 2010)

Aside from the inevitable physical injury or death, law enforcers deal with countless stressful and unceasing issues, they are continuously exposed into witnessing upsetting scenarios of murder, assault, abuse and others. The inherent dangers of law enforcement considered them a “high risk” occupational group for which the likelihood to experience extensive physical and mental health consequences, multiple psychological and emotional traumas as a consequence of work-related experiences to grave events have a negative impact on law enforcers’ performance, and interactions with citizens (Grant, Lavery, Johnson, 2019).

It is vital for police officers to remain in homeostasis for optimal police functioning, hence, resiliency as a protective tool against police stress is considered in this study. Fundamental themes of resilience are dealing with difficulty and trauma (Johnston et al. 2015; Pangallo et al. 2015), positive adaptation and a dynamic process (Aburn et al. 2016) which means resilience is both a predictor and a process variable (Britt et al. 2016; Hu et al. 2015) to an outcome (Bowler et al. 2012). In other words, resilience is seen as the ability to “bounce back” after a difficulty, but also to have the ability to cope with future situations (Paton et al. 2008 cited by Janssens et al., 2021). Lee et al. in 2016 conducted research on self-resilience as a protective factor against occurrence of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms in police officer revealed that those with low self-resilience had significantly higher rate of PTSD symptoms than those with high self-resilience. Resilience as a psychological capital describes an individual’s positive psychological state of development, illustrated by determination toward achieving goals by having the confidence (efficacy) to bounce back from adversity (resilience). The construct of resilience as a psychological capital referred to as the HERO within (Avey, Luthans, Youssef, 2010). Resilience, then has a positive impact in reducing impact of stress, hence, it is a viable resource and mechanism that promotes recovery from stressful police work, hence, promoting well-being and desirable attitudes, behaviors, and performance (Malumbwa, 2010 cited by Murray, 2020). Overall, an increase in resiliency has been associated with less intensive distress in policemen (Velichkovsky 2009).

Methodology

Respondents

The study utilized a descriptive-correlation research design. The respondents of this study are the Regional Mobile Force Battalion (RMFB) in Region 02, Philippines. The RMFB was created as the mobile reaction unit of the Philippine National Police Regional Office for Internal Security Operations, as well as to reinforce and support the Provincial, City, and Municipal Police Units for Public Safety Operations. A total sample of two hundred ninety-six (296) took part in this study.

Instrument

The Operational Police Stress Questionnaire (PSQ-OP) by McCreary and Thompson (2006) was utilized to determine the level of the respondents’ operational stress which measures work-related and social-related issues associated with law enforcement. For use in this study, the PSQ-OP was pretested to other police officers not included in the study to determine its psychometric properties as to its reliability and validity before proceeding to its use to target respondents of the study. The PSQ-OP after computing for its Cronbach alpha gave a high reliability score of .918. For use in this study, the Operational Police Stress Questionnaire’s likert scale was modified to a 4-point likert scale of 1-no stress at all which mean zero level of stress; 2-little stress which indicate a low level of stress; 3-moderate stress which show a moderate level of stress and 4-a lot of stress which mean a high level of stress.

While level of resiliency was measured by the Professional Quality of Life Scale (ProQOL) (Stamm, 2009) Version 5. It is a 30-item questionnaire which measures the three discrete psychometric scales involved in measuring the resilience among law enforcers, these are compassion satisfaction, burnout and secondary trauma stress.

The pleasure acquired from being able to help others as a part of the job is referred to as having compassion satisfaction. On the other hand, when these are not met, burnout is one component of the negative effects of caring and helping. It reflects a feeling despite all efforts made make no difference which can be related with extremely high workload or a non-supportive work environment. Furthermore, secondary trauma stress means secondary exposure to severe stressful events. For instance, exposure to traumatic events due to the demands of the job.

For use in this study, the Professional Quality of Life Scale (ProQOL) responses were modified on a four-point Likert scale (1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, or 4 = Often). It was pretested to police officers not part of the study, computed Cronbach alpha gave a high reliability score with .914. To further determine level of resiliency, scores are calculated by adding the raw scores of each of the measures of resiliency.

Data were analyzed employing computed mean to determine the operational stress and resiliency of the respondents. Moreover, chi-square was used to investigate the relationship between respondents’ operational stress experienced in their line of work and level of resiliency.

For the study’s ethical consideration, respondents opted for non-disclosure of their identity, hence the questionnaire specified that

indicating their names is optional and in reporting of data, responses were not reported individually, instead, data were reported as aggregate or group score. Also, a non-discriminatory process in selecting sample population was exercised since respondents are selected through proportional allocation where the general population is considered. An informed consent was also administered to respondents of the study stating that their participation is their own volition, that they are not coerced and have the right to withdraw anytime without any judgement.

Procedure

The research questionnaires underwent process of tool validation wherein it the survey questionnaires were pretested to police officers not part of the study. A request letter for the approval of data gathering was addressed to the Regional Director through the Force Commander of the Mobile Force Battalion was forwarded. After approval, the survey questionnaires were personally administered by the researcher, the objectives of the current study were explained thoroughly to the RMFB to assure that all items in the questionnaires were treated with utmost importance. Considering the nature of work of the respondents, some survey questionnaires were not retrieved the same day it was administered, but were retrieved after few days.

Ethical Considerations

In upholding anonymity of respondents, a non-disclosure of their identity in the questionnaire was optional and in reporting of data, responses were not reported individually, instead, data were reported as aggregate or group score. To preserve the ethical principle on doing no harm to human participants, a non-discriminatory process in selecting sample population was exercised since respondents are selected through proportional allocation where the general population is considered. An informed consent was also administered to respondents of the study stating that their participation is their own volition, that they are not coerced and have the right to withdraw anytime without any judgement.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Respondents' Level of Operational Stress*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. Shift work	1.76	Little stress
2. Working alone at night	1.97	Little stress
3. Over-time demands	2.02	Little stress
4. Risk of being injured on the job	2.21	Little stress
5. Work-related activities on days off (e.g., court, community events)	1.84	Little stress
6. Traumatic events (example: vehicular accidents, domestics, death, injury)	2.07	Little stress
7. Managing your social life outside of work	1.66	Little stress
8. Not enough time available to spend with friends and family	1.91	Little stress
9. Paperwork	1.85	Little stress
10. Eating healthy at work	1.61	Little stress
11. Finding time to stay in good physical condition	1.59	Little stress
12. Fatigue (e.g., shift work, overtime)	2.03	Little stress
13. Occupation-related health issues (e.g. back pain)	1.86	Little stress
14. Lack of understanding from family and friends about your work	1.80	Little stress
15. Making friends outside the job	1.60	Little stress
16. Upholding a "higher image" in public	1.69	Little stress
17. Negative comments from the public	1.84	Little stress
18. Limitations to your social life (e.g., who your friends are, where you socialize)	1.75	Little stress
19. Feeling like you are always on the job	1.73	Little stress
20. Friends/family feel the effects of the stigma associated with your job	1.76	Little stress
Grand Mean	1.83	Low level of stress

As gleaned from the table, the operational stresses caused by the identified aspects of police officer's work have computed means ranging from 1.60-2.21 which is interpreted to be having little stress, the grand mean of 1.83 suggests a low level of stress. It can be noted however that the highest among all the indicators of their operational stress is the "risk of being injured on the job".

Table 2. *Respondents' Level of Resiliency*

<i>Measures of Resiliency</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Compassion satisfaction	32	High Compassion Satisfaction	High level of resiliency
Burnout	28.41	Moderate Burnout	Moderate level of resiliency
Secondary Trauma Stress	24.38	Moderate Secondary Stress Trauma	Moderate level of resiliency

The respondents' level of compassion satisfaction is at a high level with a total mean score of 32 while both burnout and secondary trauma stress have moderate level with total mean scores of 28.41 and 24.38 respectively.

As seen in the table 3, compassion satisfaction, burnout and secondary trauma stress as measures of resiliency appeared to have a significant relationship with operational stress as evident in its chi values of 91.55; 70.41 and 71.36 with p-values of .000; 0.30 and

.025 respectively. Hence, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between operational stress and resiliency is rejected.

Table 3. *Relationship Between Operational Stress and Resiliency*

	<i>Measures of Resiliency</i>					
	<i>Compassion Satisfaction</i>		<i>Burnout</i>		<i>Secondary Trauma Stress</i>	
	<i>X²</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>X²</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>X²</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Operational Stress	91.55*	.000	70.41*	0.30	71.36*	.025
	Level of Significance .05		Decision: Ho is rejected			

Respondents' Level of Operational Stress

The incidence of job-related injury is distressing the law enforcement officers, in fact, West et al., (2018) concluded in their study on the perceived level of police stress that injury is common within police environment and recurring injury brought about by transportation/vehicular incidents is linked with higher perceived stress, their study specifically mentioned that due to exposure to multiple critical incidents, police stressor includes the risk of being seriously injured or killed.

The result of the study illustrates that the low level of operational stress reported by the Regional Mobile Force Battalion of Region 02, Philippines suggests that the perceived threat/stress anent to their basic function to serve and protect is foreseeable. Contrary to the various literatures that stated police work is physically demanding and emotionally depleting, dangerous, and stressful (Yoo & Franke, 2011) and considered as the top three (3) most stressed professions reported by occupational physicians and psychiatrists (Collins & Gibbs, 2003 cited by Korre, et al., 2014), they expect the dangers anent the tasks laid on them during operations as well as organizational concerns and personal issues that they have to endure indicative by their low level of operational stress.

The overall low level of operational stress is attributed to the predetermined training frameworks that play a vital part in the advancement of police officers. The training of police officers is complex that it combines numerous educational elements governed by organizational guidelines (Kleygrewe, Oudejans, Koedijk & Hutter, 2022). Wilson et al., (2010) mentioned that the entire beginning of a police officers' career is spent in training and preparing for the job, in fact, police cadets may devote a long period of time in basic training before they are accepted as police officers and encounter job-specific situations independently. In the Philippines, new recruits are required to undergo the six-month-long Public Safety Basic Recruit Course. They will also have to undergo the six months Field Training Program. Before deployment of the new police officers to their real duties, they will have to undergo more trainings to better prepare and equip them for their assignment in the field.

To combat these inherent events with police work, they are trained and prepared in dealing with shift work, working alone at night, demands for overtime, work-related tasks on day-offs, traumatic situations, handling social life, insufficient personal time, paper works, occupational-health related issues, keeping higher profile in public and negative remarks from public. Their fear of the risk of getting injured in the job though reported to be of a little stress, however got the highest mean, this is seen to be brought about by their human nature of the basic instinct to avoid pain. They may be trained to endure all pain but psychologically, all men are by nature whether conscious or unconscious has a motivational hedonism that governs human behavior to desire pleasure and avoid pain.

This long and exhausting period of basic training indicate that police officers respond to varied and multifaceted demands of their daily duty (Gershon et al., 2009), which signify that they are well equipped and prepared of the dangers and stresses associated to their tasks. Agreeing to the result of the current study is a study conducted with police officers in the Province of Antique (Espartero, 2023) which found despite having moderate level of operational stress among the respondents, they can cope with work-related concerns due to several stressors, whether in their operational or organizational functions, indicative of effective management of stress instilled by previous police trainings.

To protect people from injustice, to apprehend the criminals, to serve the people, keep law and order are common responses among those who want to enter the law enforcement, but policing is more than that, it requires a steadfast physique and mentality to combat professional obstacles in order to achieve the goals of serving and protecting the society from harm and injustice. Along this journey, police officers encounter various operational stresses that must not be ignored.

Respondents' Level of Resiliency

The respondents' level of compassion satisfaction is at a high level which means they have a high level of resiliency. This result gives a positive impression that the RMFB of Region 02, Philippines adheres to their sworn duty to serve and protect with greater concern and empathy despite its greater responsibility. Compassion satisfaction is about the pleasure the respondents acquire from being able to do his/her work well. It involves pleasure to help others through their work; feel positively about their colleagues and their capability to be part of the work setting or even the greater good of society (Stamm, 2009). The positive aspects to the role of policing or caregiving are known as a term introduced by Stamm (2002) as compassion satisfaction, which denotes to the feelings of amplified motivation and satisfaction from helping those who are in dire need. When a helping professional experience compassion satisfaction, he feels effective and highly satisfied when working with people who are helpless and traumatized and that this is attributed with heightened job commitment, performance, and quality of life. Hence, higher scores on this scale signify a greater satisfaction associated to their capability to be effective in their performance.

Conversely, the level of burnout reported by the RFMB is on a moderate level which equates to a moderate level of resiliency. Considering the common notion that the field of law enforcement is a very exhausting profession, the moderate level of burnout is somehow expected. Same result was generated by Arcega and Cabellero (2019) in their study with burnout in the Philippine National Police, they concluded that police officers experience between moderate to high level of burnout. Burnout is characterized with feelings of hopelessness and struggles in coping with work or in doing a certain task/job effectively. These negative emotions usually have a progressive onset which reflects the feeling that efforts exerted make no difference, or they can be linked with an excessive work-related task or a non-supportive work environment (Stamm, 2009). In a nutshell, burnout is a state of physical, emotional, and mental weariness triggered by continued and extreme stress. The World Health Organization acknowledged burnout to experience more often among occupations that work with other persons, for example are the service providers who respond to the demands of the society over the years (Maslach, 2017). In other words, a response to chronic job stress is burnout (Schaufeli, 2017). Zack and Schweitzer (2008 cited by Juan & Bollecer, 2019), stated that identifying burnout in a person will most likely predict the resilience of a person who is most likely susceptible to stress.

Similarly, the respondents of this study have a moderate level of secondary trauma stress (STS) which signifies a moderate level of resiliency. In attaining a higher level of psychological function and resilience, secondary trauma stress and resilience coexist with each other (Linley & Joseph, 2014). Thus, secondary trauma stress as a dimension of resiliency is being markedly associated in defining resilience (Newland et al., 2015 cited by Juan & Bollecer, 2019). STS is secondary exposure to severe or traumatic stressful incidents. Developing difficulties caused by exposure to other's trauma is uncommon but does occur to many people who help those who have experienced extremely or traumatic stressful incidents, for example, exposure to others' traumatic events as a consequence of the job as a police officer. The symptoms of STS may include fear, difficulty falling asleep, thoughts of the images of the distressing event, or evading things that awakens the traumatic event (Stamm, 2009). The moderate level of STS experienced by the RFMB show that despite being physically and mentally trained for battlefield, it is still human nature to be feeling anxious when faced with threat to both physiological and psychological wellbeing is perceived and experienced. Secondary Trauma Stress have been documented to be attributed to risky job demands (Elwood, Mott, Lohr, Galovski, 2011). Conforming to this result is the study conducted by Mara, Zito & Colombo (2020) they found that compared with health care workers, police officers suffer from secondary trauma stress (negative emotions and burnout) to a greater extent.

With the aforementioned data gathered, revealed that having high Compassion Satisfaction combined with moderate burnout and Secondary Trauma Stress levels represents a more positive behavioral outcome and intricate ability to bounce back from a stressful situation (Stamm, 2010). Self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1997) coincides with this result, from this perspective, police officers' ability to bounce back is seen as the consequence of a dynamic interplay of personal, behavioral, and environmental influences.

Relationship Between Operational Stress and Resiliency

The result of the present study revealed a significant relationship between operational stress and resiliency. It suggests that when a police officer's compassion satisfaction is high, he may likely to experience little or low operational stress, hence resilience is high. Compassion satisfaction has been introduced by Stamm (2002) as a protective factor against the development of stress. It is an internal feeling of increased motivation and fulfillment resulting from helping those who suffer. Subsequently, it qualifies as an important form of internal "recovery capital." Granfield and Cloud (1999 cited by Lavery, Grant & Decarlo, 2019) argue that recovery capital includes internal resources (compassion, empathy and motivation) used by an individual to get through stress. Conforming to this result is the study conducted by Piotrowski, Sygit-Kowalkowska, Boe & Rawat (2022) where they concluded that as resilience increases, the occupational stress decreases.

Burnout as a dimension of resiliency appeared to have a significant relationship with operational stress which imply that when operational stress is high, burnout is also high, hence resiliency is low whereas when operational stress is low, burnout is also low, thus resiliency is high. Conforming to this result is a study conducted by Wang, Chang, Fu and Wang (2012) stated that a high level of occupational stress would have more symptoms of burnout. Burnout is an experience of emotional, physical exhaustion and reduced personal accomplishment (Maslach & Schaufeli, 2001), has been associated with prolonged exposure to job stress (Iroegbu & Nwaogwugwu, 2012) that adversely impact the functionality of police work in investigating, detecting, and managing crime (Brownson, 2012 cited by Ogungbamila & Fajemirokun, 2016). In other words, the result of chronic work-related stress is burnout, job stress then significantly predicted occupational burnout such that an increase in job stress led to increase in the level of occupational burnout (Ogungbamila & Fajemirokun, 2016).

Considering that policing is known to be a stressful occupation, which harms police officers' physical and mental health eventually eliciting burnout (Quieros et al., 2020), they may demonstrate greater resiliency to stress than the general public (Galatzer-Levy, et al., 2013, this can be attributed to the rigorous and regimented physical and mental training before entering the organization nurtured by the various programs offered by the PNP. However, prevention of the occurrence of burnout among the police officers will make job performance more fulfilling.

Furthermore, the significant relationship found between the respondents' operational stress and secondary trauma stress suggests that when the stressful experiences become overwhelming, the level of secondary trauma stress increased, thus resilience is low; while when the experience of operational stress is low, the level of secondary trauma stress decreased which means resilience level is high.

To name a few of the numerous stressful incidents police officers are exposed to in their line of work are experiences of traumatic events such as violence, death, abused children, natural and man-made disasters are attributed to some of the highest stress levels (Korre et al., 2014).

With the high correlations between job stress and secondary trauma stress, there is a considerable likelihood that a police officer exposed to secondary trauma would report similar levels of job stress (Cieslak et al., 2014). Other related research also found that there was a statistically significant relationship between the stress brought about by type of crime (for example: family violence, child protection and sexual offences) which could make police officers experience symptoms of secondary traumatic stress (Cronje & Vilakazi, 2020). With these results, secondary trauma stress as a dimension of resilience is significantly associated, thus, mitigating the occurrence of secondary trauma stress among police officers is the central core of having high level of resiliency.

Conclusions

With the findings of the study, insights derived that the low level of operational stress reported by Regional Mobile Force Battalion of Region 02, Philippines is attributed to the foreseeable threat or stress anent to their basic function to serve and protect. During the course of policing, they are trained and prepared in dealing with shift work, working alone at night, the need for overtime, work-related activities on day-offs, traumatic incidents, coping with social life, insufficient personal time, paper works, occupational-health related issues, upholding higher image in public and negative comments from public. Thus, the complex regimented and rigorous training frameworks that operates within various educational components governed by organizational guidelines play a crucial role in the development of a physically and mentally tough police officers.

In police culture where they are expected to be resilient at all cost, resilience (as measured by the police officers' compassion satisfaction, burnout and secondary trauma stress) then is seen in the context of exposure to significant adversity, as when a police officer's compassion satisfaction is high, he may likely to experience little or low operational stress, hence resilience is high. On the other hand, when operational stress is high, burnout is also high, hence resiliency is low whereas when operational stress is low, burnout is also low, thus resiliency is high. In addition, when the stressful experiences become overwhelming, the level of secondary trauma stress increased, thus resilience is low; while when the experience of operational stress is low, the level of secondary trauma stress decreased which means resilience level is high. It can therefore be concluded that to have the capacity to recover from operational stress, there should be high compassion satisfaction combined with moderate levels of burnout and secondary trauma stress. This embodies a more positive behavioral outcome to recuperate from a stressful situation.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the results of the study, the following are recommended:

The Regional Mobile Force to consider a routine assessment of operational stress among the RFMB. This will serve as benchmark data for identifying who needs immediate concern to mitigate occurrence of a maladjusted behavior.

Learning to be resilient in all adversities were taught during police trainings, however, a continuous program for resiliency as a form of debriefing after a grave incident may be considered.

Future research may conduct the same study to explore more on the qualitative inquiry on police operational stress and resiliency.

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